

1 **DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF AN ANALYTICAL METHODOLOGY**
2 **BASED ON SOLVENT MICROEXTRACTION AND UHPLC-MS/MS FOR**
3 **DETERMINING BISPHENOLS IN HONEYS FROM DIFFERENT BOTANICAL**
4 **ORIGINS**

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11 **Abstract**

12 A new analytical methodology was proposed to determine fourteen bisphenols in honeys from
13 different botanical origins using ultra-high performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass
14 spectrometry. A fast, efficient, environmentally-friendly and simple sample treatment
15 (recoveries between 81% and 116%; matrix effect < 20% for all studied compounds except for
16 bisphenol E, F and S) was proposed, which involved a solvent microextraction with acetone
17 and a small volume/amount of 1-hexanol. Chromatographic analysis (< 15 min) was performed
18 in a Kinetex EVO C₁₈ column under gradient elution mode. The method was validated in terms
19 of selectivity, limits of detection (0.2–1.5 µg/kg) and quantification (0.5–4.7 µg/kg), linearity,
20 matrix effect, trueness, and precision (relative standard deviation < 17%). Finally, thirty honey
21 samples were analyzed, revealing the presence of residues of nine bisphenols in some of them.
22 However, quantification was possible only in two cases for bisphenol A, with a concentration
23 of approximately 13 µg/kg.

24

25 **Keywords:** bisphenols; food safety; green analytical chemistry; honey; UHPLC-MS/MS;
26 method validation; sample treatment.

27 **1. Introduction**

28 Bisphenols (BPs), which are organic compounds with two phenol functional groups, are used
29 as additives to improve durability, flexibility and temperature resistance of plastics (Lestido-
30 Cardama, Vázquez Loureiro, Sendón, Paseiro Losada, & Bernaldo de Quirós, 2021; Priovolos,
31 & Samanidou, 2023). The best-known is bisphenol A (BPA), a monomer used in the production
32 of polycarbonate plastics and epoxy resins, which are commonly used in the manufacture of
33 food packaging (Shaaban et al., 2022). BPA is a dangerous substance, recognized as an
34 endocrine disruptor, which can cause serious problems at very low doses (Abraham &
35 Chakraborty, 2019). Although the effects of endocrine disruptors on human health are not yet
36 fully understood, their effects on women are especially serious. BPA has structural similarity
37 to some hormones, especially those that control breast development (Martín-Gómez, Elmore,
38 Valverde, Ares, & Bernal, 2024). Therefore, BPA exposure can lead to the proliferation of
39 cancer cells in breast tissue (He et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2021). Additionally, exposure during
40 pregnancy can have adverse effects on the neural development of the fetus, increasing the risk
41 of diabetes and heart disease (Aris, 2014). Moreover, exposure to BPA has been associated with
42 an increased risk of spontaneous abortions (Liang et al., 2020). It should be mentioned that
43 there is a wide range of BPA analogues, such as bisphenol AF (BPAF), bisphenol AP (BPAP),
44 bisphenol B (BPB), bisphenol BP (BPBP), bisphenol C (BPC), bisphenol E (BPE), bisphenol
45 F (BPF), bisphenol FL (BPFL), bisphenol M (BPM), bisphenol P (BPP), bisphenol PH (BPPH),
46 bisphenol S (BPS), and bisphenol Z (BPZ), whose structures are shown in **Figure 1S** (see
47 Supplementary Material). These analogues are currently used as substitutes for BPA; however,
48 they also pose a health risk due to their demonstrated genotoxicity and estrogenic activity,
49 similar to that of BPA (Liao et al., 2012; Priovolos, & Samanidou, 2023). The European
50 Commission has established specific migration limits (SMLs) for BPA from varnishes or
51 coatings into or onto food at 0.05 mg/kg of food, thereby prohibiting the use of BPA in articles

52 intended for infants and young children (European Commission, 2018). However, as of now,
53 no SMLs have been established for BPA analogues, except for BPS (0.05 mg/kg; European
54 Commission, 2011).

55

56 This work focuses on the analysis of BPs in honey, which is a natural food made by bees from
57 the nectar of flowers. Honey is one of the most complex natural foods, since it contains around
58 400 substances, such as carbohydrates, proteins, amino acids, phenolic compounds and
59 vitamins, among others (Valverde, Ares, Stephen Elmore, & Bernal, 2022). All these
60 compounds make the consumption of honey very beneficial for health. Indeed, honey has
61 antioxidant, healing, anti-inflammatory, therapeutic, nutritional, antimicrobial and antidiabetic
62 properties, making its consumption highly recommended (Notardonato et al., 2020a; Rana et
63 al., 2018). Although BPs are not compounds that are found naturally in honey, it is possible for
64 them to contaminate it, since honey bees interact with plants, air, soil, and water in close
65 proximity to the hive. Therefore, if these matrices are contaminated with BPs, these compounds
66 may be transferred to honey bees and, ultimately, find their way into hive products, including
67 honey (Naggar et al., 2021). Moreover, like any food product, honey could potentially contain
68 BPs, since these compounds may migrate from the packaging into the honey (Česen et al.,
69 2016). Therefore, it is reasonable to propose the hypothesis that, given the potential of honey
70 to present residues of BPs, there is a need for the development of specific and sensitive
71 methodologies for their determination at low concentrations. In addition, the ubiquity of BPs in
72 the laboratory underscores that special attention must be paid to minimizing this contamination
73 in order to guarantee accurate analysis of the samples (Ballesteros-Gómez, Rubio, & Pérez-
74 Bendito, 2009; Martín-Gómez et al., 2024).

75

76 Current methods for the analysis of BPs in honey are predominantly based on chromatographic
77 techniques such as high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) or gas chromatography
78 (GC; Martín-Gómez et al., 2024; see Supplementary Material, **Table 1S**). However, due to the
79 low volatility of BPs owing to their high boiling points (> 200 °C), analysis of BPs by GC
80 requires some derivatization steps involving alkylation, silylation or acylation before
81 chromatographic separation. These additional steps imply an increase in analysis time and, in
82 addition, decrease the reproducibility of the method and introduce a possible source of
83 contamination (Lestido-Cardama et al., 2021). HPLC can be coupled with fluorescence (FLD)
84 and diode array (DAD) detectors, which offer advantages such as simplicity and low cost.
85 However, to improve selectivity and sensitivity when analyzing BPs at low concentrations in a
86 complex matrix, like honey, it is more convenient to use HPLC coupled to mass spectrometry
87 (MS) and, specifically, tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS; see Supplementary Material,
88 **Table 1S**). Concerning the most commonly employed sample treatments to determine BPs in
89 honey, an analysis of the existing literature (see Supplementary Material, **Table 1S**) indicates
90 that solid phase extraction (SPE) with polymeric sorbents (Česen et al., 2016; Inoue et al., 2003;
91 Lo Turco et al., 2016; Zhou et al., 2019) and dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction (DLLME)
92 alone or in combination with other techniques such as ultrasound (Khani, Khandaghi,
93 Farajzadeh, Reza, & Mogaddam, 2021; Meng, Li, Wang, & Cao, 2022; Notardonato et al.,
94 2020; Peñalver, Arroyo-Manzanares, Campillo, & Viñas, 2021) predominate. Other
95 alternatives, like molecularly imprinted solid phase extraction employing a specifically
96 prepared molecularly imprinted polymer with BPA as template and 4-vinylpyridine as the
97 functional monomer (Herrero-Hernández, Carabias-Martínez, & Rodríguez-Gonzalo, 2009), a
98 restricted-access material (alkyl-diol-silica) coupled on-line to a HPLC-MS/MS (Rodríguez-
99 Gonzalo, García-Gómez, & Carabias-Martínez, 2010), or aqueous biphasic systems coupled
100 with HPLC-FLD (Tian, Bai, & Xu, 2018), were also employed in some studies. It can also be

101 deduced from the study of **Table 1S** (see Supplementary Material) that many of the proposed
102 methods are not exclusive to either BPs or honey, and except for one work (Česen et al., 2016),
103 more than four BPs have not been simultaneously investigated in honey. Furthermore, there is
104 no evidence of an HPLC-MS/MS method in which the matrix effect was not relevant for any
105 of the studied BPs, nor of a method in which its suitability for honeys from different origins has
106 been tested, which is a relevant issue according to our experience (Fuente-Ballesteros et al.,
107 2023).

108
109 Therefore, the main goal of the present study is to propose a method for determining
110 simultaneously fourteen BPs (BPA, BPAF, BPAP, BPB, BPBP, BPC, BPE, BPF, BPFL, BPM,
111 BPP, BPPH, BPS, and BPZ) in honeys from three different botanical origins (multifloral,
112 rosemary, and heather). An ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography (UHPLC)-MS/MS
113 instrument was selected for the analysis, due to its potential for achieving better resolutions and
114 sensitivities, as well as shorter running times, thereby implying reduced solvent consumption
115 (Alarcón-Flores, Romero-González, Vidal, & Frenich, 2013). Another objective of this work is
116 to propose an efficient, simple, cheap and fast sample treatment applicable to honeys from
117 different origins. These conditions aim to ensure good recoveries, minimize the potential matrix
118 effect, and adhere as closely as possible to the principles of green analytical chemistry,
119 specifically by reducing time, cost, steps, and reagents, or avoiding derivatization procedures
120 (Gałaszka, Migaszewski, & Namieśnik, 2013). To the best of our knowledge, this is the first
121 study in which an analytical methodology has been proposed for determining BPs in different
122 types of honey. Our study also aims to validate the proposed method in accordance with current
123 European legislation (EURACHEM, 2014) and analyse experimental and commercial honey
124 samples from the aforementioned origins.

125

126 2. Materials and methods

127 2.1. Reagents and materials

128 BP standards (BPA, BPA-d₁₆, BPAF, BPAP, BPB, BPBP, BPC, BPE, BPF, BPFL, BPM, BPP,
129 BPPH, BPS, BPZ; see structures in Supplementary Material, **Figure 1S**), all of analytical-grade
130 and with purity greater than 98%, were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Chemie Gbmh
131 (Steinheim, Germany). All solvents and reagents were of chromatographic/analytical grade and
132 obtained from VWR Prolabo Chemicals (Fontenay-sous-Bois, France; acetonitrile, hexane and
133 methanol), Carlo Erba Reagents-SA (Milan, Italy; acetone, ammonia, ammonium acetate, ethyl
134 acetate and tetrahydrofuran), and Sigma-Aldrich Chemie Gbmh (Steinheim, Germany; 1-
135 hexanol, formic acid, magnesium sulfate, methyl tert-butyl ether, sodium chloride, and sodium
136 sulfate). Ultrapure water was obtained using Millipore Milli-RO plus and Milli-Q systems
137 (Bedford, MA, USA). A vortex mechanical mixer from Heidolph (Schwabach, Germany), a
138 thermostated ultrasound bath, a drying oven, and a vibromatic mechanical shaker, all supplied
139 by J.P. Selecta S.A. (Barcelona, Spain), a 5810 R refrigerated bench-top centrifuge from
140 Eppendorf (Hamburg, Germany), a R-3 rotary evaporator from Buchi (Flawil, Switzerland),
141 and Nylon syringe filters (17 mm, 0.45 µm; Nalgene, Rochester, NY) were employed for
142 sample treatment. Bond Elu NH₂ (3 mL, 500 mg of sorbent; Agilent, CA, USA), Oasis HLB (3
143 mL, 60 mg; Waters, Milford, MA, USA), Strata[®] X (3 mL or 6 mL, 100 or 200 mg;
144 Phenomenex, Torrance, CA), Strata SCX (3 mL, 500 mg of sorbent; Phenomenex, Torrance,
145 CA); Isolute HMN (5 mL, 3.5 g; Biotage Sweden AB, Uppsala, Sweden) cartridges, and a 10-
146 port Visiprep vacuum manifold (Supelco, Bellefonte, PA), were used for the SPE extractions.

147 It should be highlighted that, due to the common presence of BPs in the laboratory environment,
148 their potential presence in the background signal values of blanks must be controlled (Peñalver
149 et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2019). For example, the plastic consumables (pipettes and centrifuge
150 tubes) and chemical reagents were newly used/opened, and the absence of BPs' residues was

151 previously confirmed. Moreover, laboratory glassware was carefully and sequentially washed
152 with ultrapure water, nitric acid, and ultrapure water again, followed by a final wash with a
153 mixture of acetone and methanol (1:1, v/v) before being dried in an oven at around 100°C for
154 60 min. Procedural blanks, in which ultrapure water substituted honey, were run between sets
155 of samples to monitor potential abnormal background values.

156 2.2. Standards

157 Standard stock (≈ 1000 mg/L) and working solutions of BPs, including the IS, were prepared
158 in methanol. Honey samples, in which the absence of BPs had been previously confirmed using
159 UHPLC-MS/MS (blank samples) were spiked with variable amounts of the analytes either
160 before (BF samples) or after (AF samples) sample treatment (see Subsection 2.3) to prepare the
161 standard in matrix extracts. The spiking of the samples was done similarly to Fuente-Ballesteros
162 et al., 2023 (see Supplementary Material, **Table 2S**), and the internal standard (IS; BPA-d₁₆)
163 was consistently added at the same concentration (0.1 mg/L). It should be mentioned that the
164 IS was not added from the beginning of the sample treatment but at the reconstitution stage in
165 the final method, as BPs were extracted in all cases with high efficiency and precision (see
166 Subsection 3.3.6), and what was intended to compensate was the variability in the intensity of
167 the MS/MS signals characteristic of this technique due to differences in ionization efficiency.
168 These samples were used for validation (spiked samples (low, medium, and high) and
169 calibration curves), as well as for sample treatment studies. It is important to note that three
170 replicates from each origin, which were injected three times, were prepared for all the above-
171 mentioned studies. Each spiked sample was prepared with 1 g of blank honey sample spiked
172 with three different concentrations of the BPs within the linear range. These were as follows:
173 low-LOQ (see **Table 1**); medium-50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$; high-250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$. The standard stock solutions were
174 stored in glass containers in darkness at -20 °C, and working and standard matrix solutions were
175 stored in glass containers and kept in the dark at +4 °C. Finally, it must be highlighted that no

176 differences were observed in the stability of the deuterated IS (BPA-d₁₆) with respect to that of
177 the rest of the BPs, since they remained stable in all cases for more than four weeks, and
178 consequently the way of working with the IS was exactly the same as with the other BPs. To
179 check this point, the working solutions were periodically injected with the mixture of all the
180 BPs and the IS and it was checked if there were variations in the peak parameters (area, height,
181 width) and analyte/IS peak area ratios.

182 2.3. Sample procurement and treatment

183 2.3.1. Samples

184 Honey samples ($n = 30$) were generously donated by beekeepers from different Spanish regions
185 (Castilla y León, País Vasco) and the Center for Agroenvironmental and Apicultural
186 Investigation (CIAPA; Marchamalo, Guadalajara, Spain), or purchased from local markets
187 (Valladolid, Spain; Helsinki, Finland; Tallin, Estonia). They were selected based on their origin
188 (multifloral, rosemary, heather), and their different colors (white, light amber, and dark amber;
189 see Supplementary Material, **Table 3S**). Moreover, the botanical origin of the CIAPA samples
190 that were used as blank samples was confirmed by melissopalynological analysis and
191 corresponded to rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*; three samples); multifloral (three samples),
192 and heather (*Erica spp*; three samples). It must be specified that in this work we have decided
193 to select honey from three botanical origins (multifloral, rosemary, heather), to develop and
194 validate the method for the following reasons: **i**) they have very different compositions and
195 physicochemical characteristics. So, if the method is valid for these botanical origins, it would
196 be probably valid for other types of honey. This allows increasing the relevance, validity, and
197 interest of the proposed method; **ii**) these are three of the botanical origins that are most found
198 in supermarkets and produced by beekeepers. This allows obtaining sufficient quantities and
199 numbers of samples to carry out the development and validation of the methods. Meanwhile, a
200 HI96785 honey color portable photometer (Hanna Instruments, Woonsocket, RI, USA) was

201 used to determine the color of honey. For homogenization, each sample underwent individual
202 stirring with a glass rod and was then stored in separate tubes in darkness at 4 °C until analysis.
203 Three replicates (sub-samples) of each honey sample, injected in triplicate, were examined to
204 determine the BP content.

205 *2.3.2. Sample treatment*

206 Briefly, 1.0 g of homogenized honey was weighed in a 50 mL centrifuge tube, after which 1
207 mL of ultrapure water was added, and the tube was shaken for 30 s in a vortex device. Next,
208 1.5 mL of acetone, 35 µL of 1-hexanol, and 500 mg of magnesium sulfate mixture were added
209 to the tube and then put in an ultrasound bath for 5 min. After that, the mixture was centrifuged
210 (4000 rpm; 5 °C) for 5 min. The upper phase (organic) was collected and evaporated to dryness
211 at 60 °C in a rotary evaporator. Finally, the dry extract was reconstituted with 0.5 mL of an IS
212 solution (0.1 mg/L) in methanol, and it was passed through a 0.45 µm nylon filter prior UHPLC-
213 MS/MS analysis.

214 *2.4. UHPLC-MS/MS parameters*

215 UHPLC-MS/MS analyses were carried out using a UHPLC Sciex Exion system connected to a
216 Sciex 6500+ triple quadrupole mass spectrometer from Sciex (Washington, DC, USA). The
217 mass spectrometer was equipped with an electrospray ionization (ESI) source and operated in
218 negative mode. Chromatographic separation was accomplished using a reversed phase column,
219 Kinetex EVO C₁₈ (2.1 mm × 50 mm, 1.7 µm), protected with a Kinetex EVO C₁₈ guard column,
220 both from Phenomenex (Torrance, CA, USA). Mobile phase was composed of 10 mM
221 ammonium acetate in ultrapure water (solvent A) and methanol (solvent B) at a flow rate of 0.3
222 mL/min in the following gradient mode: (i) 0.0 min (A–B, 50:50, v/v); (ii) 1.0 min (A–B, 50:50,
223 v/v); (iii) 5.0 min (A–B, 15:85, v/v); (iv) 11.0 min (A–B, 15:85, v/v); (v) 13.0 min (A–B, 50:50,
224 v/v); (vi) 15.0 min (A–B, 50:50, v/v). Injection volume and column temperature were set at 3

225 μL and $15\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. With such conditions, the overall run time was 15 min (see **Figure**
226 **1**). For mass spectrometry acquisition, multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) mode was
227 employed. This mode recorded the transitions between the precursor ion and the most abundant
228 product ions for each target analyte (see conditions and transitions in **Table 2**). Additionally,
229 the ESI operational settings were as follows: capillary voltage, -4500 V ; capillary temperature,
230 $300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; ion source gas 1 and 2 pressure, 80 psi and 60 psi , respectively; curtain gas, 35 psi ;
231 collision gas, 9 psi . SciexOS software was employed for data acquisition and evaluation.

232

233 **3. Results and discussion**

234 3.1. Optimization of the sample treatment

235 As mentioned in the introduction, the most used sample treatments when determining BPs in
236 honey were SPE and DLLME (see Supplementary Material, **Table 1S**). However, considering
237 our objective to propose a procedure that is simple, fast, and minimizes the consumption of
238 reagents, we also explored extraction using supramolecular solvents (SUPRAS). SUPRAS are
239 green water-immiscible solvents that are made up of aggregates of amphiphilic compounds,
240 which are substances with a hydrophilic and a hydrophobic part. SUPRAS usually provide very
241 high extraction yields in a short time, and, in addition, provide extracts clean enough to be
242 analyzed directly without the need for additional cleaning steps (Ballesteros-Gómez,
243 Ballesteros, & Rubio, 2024). Typically, SUPRAS are prepared by mixing amphiphilic
244 compounds (such as long-chain alcohols) in appropriate proportions with water and a water-
245 miscible solvent, which is usually tetrahydrofuran (THF). To promote the formation of these
246 solvents, variations of temperature, pH, or the addition of an inorganic salt can be considered
247 (Ballesteros-Gómez et al., 2024; Musarurwa & Tavengwa, 2021). The optimization process
248 began with a multifloral honey (light amber) spiked at medium concentration ($50\text{ }\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$; BPs

249 free-blank, AF and BF samples; see Subsection 2.2). Firstly, we assessed the suitability of SPE
250 for analyzing BPs in honey, employing a common procedure in almost all cases. This involved
251 preconditioning the cartridges before passing the sample, which was usually a dilution with
252 ultrapure water, followed by a washing step, drying time, and a final elution stage. A
253 concentration step was then performed using rotary evaporation and, finally, reconstitution in
254 1 mL of the solution of the corresponding standards in methanol. During the SPE tests, various
255 types of sorbents were tested, including polymeric, anionic, cationic and adsorption cartridges.
256 The detailed results are provided in **Table 3**. The first tests (T1–T4) were carried out
257 exclusively with BPA in order to simplify the optimization procedure, as it is the most relevant
258 BP. Polymeric SPE cartridges were initially checked, as they were predominantly employed for
259 determining BPs in honey. Consequently, Oasis HLB (60 mg) cartridges were evaluated, and
260 two different methods were tested for this cartridge (T1 and T2). Results were slightly better in
261 terms of extraction efficiency and matrix effect for T2, in which methanol was selected as
262 preconditioning and elution solvent. Thus, the method that used ethyl acetate was discarded.
263 The same SPE conditions used for P2 were tested with the Strata X polymeric cartridge with
264 two different amounts of sorbent, 100 mg (T3) and 200 mg (T4), and it was found that the
265 recovery percentage with the 100 mg sorbent was much lower, although the matrix effect was
266 slightly better than with 200 mg. Consequently, we decided to continue the SPE optimization
267 with all the BPs employing the Oasis HLB (60 mg; T5) and Strata X (200 mg; T6) cartridges.
268 Similar results were obtained for both cartridges. Oasis HLB showed recovery percentages
269 greater than 70% for eight BPs, while Strata X exhibited percentages higher than 70% for nine
270 BPs. Furthermore, the matrix effect (suppression of ionization in all cases except for BPC) was
271 very significant for all analytes. Thus, the use of polymeric cartridges was rejected due to low
272 recoveries obtained for several of the BPs, and the strong matrix effect observed for all the
273 compounds. Next, cartridges of anionic (Bond Elut NH₂, 500 mg; T7) and cationic (Strata SCX,

274 500 mg, T8) nature were tested, but in both cases much worse results were obtained in terms of
275 recovery percentages, and on top of that, many of the BPs were not retained in them. As a final
276 option, diatomaceous earth cartridges (Isolute HMN, 3.5 g) were tested. It was observed that
277 hexane, a nonpolar solvent, was only able to elute three analytes from the cartridge (T9.1).
278 However, when performing a second elution of the cartridge using methyl tert-butyl ether
279 (T9.2), peaks corresponding to all analytes could be detected. Indeed, if a third elution with
280 methyl tert-butyl ether (T9.3) was performed, peaks were also obtained for all analytes.
281 Therefore, it was concluded that a more polar solvent was required to achieve a complete elution
282 of the analytes. For this reason, it was decided to use ethyl acetate from the beginning of the
283 procedure (T10.1), which allowed the detection of peaks for all BPs. However, low recoveries
284 were observed for most of them, and when testing a second elution (P10.2), it was confirmed
285 that the analytes were still retained in the cartridge. This finding implies the necessity to use
286 larger volumes of solvent, which contravenes the principles of green analytical chemistry that
287 we aim to follow in this work. Consequently, the use of SPE was definitively ruled out, and
288 tests with modified DLLME and SUPRAS were performed. In order to try to optimize the
289 solvent extraction, two procedures selected/adapted from the literature were used. One
290 procedure (modified SUPRAS) was based on the addition of 1-hexanol and THF (Romera-
291 García, Caballero-Casero, & Rubio, 2019), while the other involved a different approach in
292 which 1-undecanol (1-hexanol in our study) and acetone were used (modified DLLME;
293 Mahdavianpour et al., 2021). It should be mentioned that the function of 1-hexanol was not
294 only to promote the extraction of BPs from honey in both sample treatments (Ballesteros-
295 Gómez, & Rubio, 2023; Habibi, Mohammadi, & Kamankesh, 2018), but also, to facilitate the
296 separation of the phases in the case of the modified DLLME approach. In this last case, the
297 extraction was achieved by the combined action of this alcohol together with acetone, which is
298 also miscible with water, and consequently, in order to differentiate and collect the organic

299 phase, 1-hexanol was needed. In this stage of the optimization procedure, different amounts of
300 honey and shaking sources/instruments (vortex, vibromatic and ultrasound) were tested. The
301 conditions and results of the most significant experiments are summarized in **Table 4**. It should
302 be remarked that a multifloral honey (light amber) spiked at medium concentration (50 µg/kg;
303 BPs free-blank, AF and BF samples; see Subsection 2.2) was selected to perform these
304 experiments. As can be seen, the best overall performance (extraction recoveries between 85%
305 and 110% for all BPs; matrix effect $< \pm 20\%$ for all compounds except for BPE, BPF and BPS)
306 was obtained in the experiment T15, in which 35 µL of 1-hexanol and 1500 µL of acetone were
307 added to 1 g of honey dissolved in 1 mL of water. BPs were extracted with the help of an
308 ultrasound for five minutes, and subsequently centrifuged at 4000 rpm for five minutes. The
309 organic phase was collected and evaporated to dryness at 60°C, and reconstituted with 0.5 mL
310 of methanol. It should be mentioned that extraction recoveries were low for many of the BPs
311 ($< 70\%$) in several of the experiments (T13, T16 and T18), and the matrix effect was also
312 significant for most BPs in many cases (T11, T12, T14, T16, T17 and T18). Consequently, it
313 was decided to check the suitability of the selected sample treatment with multifloral honey
314 samples spiked at the other two concentration levels (Low, LOQ; high, 250 µg/kg. The results
315 showed that the extraction recoveries were good enough when spiking at high concentration
316 (83%-113%), but they were slightly lower ($< 80\%$) for some of the BPs at low concentration
317 level (data not shown); meanwhile, matrix effect values were good for all BPs at all
318 concentration levels. Thus, it was decided to check if the addition of a salt could improve the
319 extraction results. Therefore, 500 mg of sodium chloride, magnesium sulfate and ammonium
320 sulfate were included in the proposed sample treatment. It was found that the addition of a salt
321 improved not only the separation of the phases but also the extraction recoveries. Particularly,
322 when using magnesium sulfate, extraction recoveries for all BPs ranged between 81% and
323 114%, while the matrix effect remained significant for the same three BPs (see **Table 5**).

324 Finally, the selected sample treatment conditions were applied to honey samples from the other
325 two botanical origins (rosemary, white; heather, dark amber) spiked at the three different
326 concentration levels (see **Table 5**). The results were quite similar to those obtained for
327 multifloral honey, as the extraction recoveries were good in all cases (81%-116%) and the
328 matrix effect caused a significant signal suppression ($> 20\%$) for BPE, BPF and BPS in all types
329 of honey. Consequently, the conditions detailed above and summarized in Subsection 2.3.2
330 were deemed definitive.

331 To sum up, the proposed sample treatment can be considered as a promising alternative to
332 previous proposals summarized in **Table 1S** (see Supplementary Material), since it is generally
333 faster, simpler (with fewer stages), and involves little use of reagents (solvents, salts/sorbents),
334 and is applicable to honeys from different botanical origins. Therefore, we may also conclude
335 that the proposed method aligns more closely with the objectives of green analytical chemistry
336 than most of those previously published. This is evident as the use of solvents and reagents is
337 among the lowest (< 2.6 mL), it avoids the use of solvents that are less environmentally friendly
338 (such as acetonitrile, toluene, or benzene), it is one of the shortest of those proposed (≈ 15 min),
339 and it is also one of the simplest; hence, it can be considered economical in comparison with
340 other proposals. Moreover, recovery values were satisfactory for all the analytes studied, and,
341 more importantly, the matrix effect was not significant for most of BPs (eleven of fourteen),
342 which is an important improvement with regard to previous studies in which MS or MS/MS
343 detectors were employed (see Supplementary Material, **Table 1S**), since in these works either
344 this parameter was not studied or it was significant for all the BPs studied. However, it should
345 be emphasized that the primary distinction and significant novelty in this context lies in the fact
346 that it can be applied to honey from different botanical origins, which are quite varied in their
347 composition. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that such an application has
348 been proposed or demonstrated.

349

350 3.2. Optimization of the UHPLC-MS/MS conditions

351 Optimization experiments were conducted with Kinetex EVO C₁₈ 100 Å (2.1 × 50 mm, 1.7 μm),
352 as C₁₈ columns were commonly employed for determining BPs in honey, and it was the
353 stationary phase selected in the only work in which UHPLC was employed (Zhou et al., 2019).
354 Kinetex EVO C₁₈ uses a patented organo-silica grafting process that incorporates uniform,
355 stabilizing ethane cross-linking. This design provides resistance to high pH attack while
356 maintaining the mechanical strength of the core shell particle. The result is higher peak
357 sensitivity and shorter overall analysis time (Phenomenex, 2018). Firstly, the MS/MS
358 conditions were optimized by injecting individual standards of the BPs with a concentration of
359 100 μg/L and varying the analyzer parameters (QqQ); meanwhile, ESI in negative mode was
360 always employed as it was predominantly selected in previous works (see Supplementary
361 Material, **Table 1S**). The conditions that provided the best signals are listed in **Table 2**. With
362 these conditions, it was possible to obtain the precursor ions and the products ions of the BPs,
363 which are detailed in **Table 2**, and that will be used in the MRM mode to carry out the
364 quantification and identification of the compounds. It should be mentioned that the initial focus
365 of optimization was on BPA, due to its greater importance. Then, several tests were carried out
366 to evaluate the separation and signal intensity of the studied BPs by using different mixtures
367 and gradient elution modes of organic and aqueous solvents as mobile phase components.
368 Methanol and acetonitrile were tested as organic solvents due to their predominance in previous
369 studies. No significant differences in peak shape or signal intensity were observed when using
370 one or the other (data not shown), but on contrary, the use of methanol was preferred as it solved
371 the co-elution problem related to BPP and BPM. Those compounds are position isomers and it
372 was not possible to separate them with acetonitrile, but when decreasing the strength of the
373 mobile phase (using methanol instead of acetonitrile), apart from a slight increase in the

374 retention time of all the analytes, both compounds were separated without affecting the
375 separation of the rest of BPs. Likewise, the effect of pH on the signal obtained was verified,
376 changing the nature of the aqueous solvent of the mobile phase (ultrapure water, pH \approx 7.0; 0.1%
377 (v/v) formic acid in ultrapure water, pH \approx 2.7; 0.01% (v/v); ammonia in ultrapure water, pH \approx
378 11.0; ammonium acetate 10 mM in ultrapure water, pH \approx 7). The latter (ammonium acetate 10
379 mM) was the one that solved the issue of low BPS retention, although the ionization of the BPs
380 was slightly worse than with ammonia 0.01%. An additional test was performed with 20 mM
381 (v/v) of ammonium acetate to evaluate whether ionization improved, but no significant
382 differences were found. Finally, it was decided to continue with 10 mM ammonium acetate in
383 the following tests. Once the mobile phase components were selected (methanol and
384 ammonium acetate 10 mM), several experiments were then conducted to test diverse mobile
385 phase gradients, variable flow rates, temperatures and injection volumes. The aim was to elute
386 all the compounds rapidly whilst preventing as far as possible co-elution between them and
387 with potential matrix components. Under optimal chromatographic conditions (see Subsection
388 2.4 and **Table 2**), all compounds eluted in less than 11 minutes (see **Figure 1**), achieving an
389 overall run time of 15 minutes. This, according to the existing literature, and considering the
390 significant influence of matrix and the number of compounds on separation, not only establishes
391 this method as the fastest proposal to date, whether GC or HPLC, for analyzing five or more
392 BPs in honey, but also represents the method that has simultaneously examined the largest
393 number of BPs in this matrix (see Supplementary Material, **Table 1S**).

394

395 3.3. Method validation

396 We performed method validation according to current legislation (EURACHEM, 2014). In
397 addition, several of the main elements of uncertainty (Konieczka & Namieśnik, 2010) were
398 considered when optimizing and validating this method (amount of sample used; recovery value

399 of the analytical procedure; precision, and repeatability). Validation was performed with blank
400 honeys, standards in the solvent, and standards in matrix extracts obtained according to the
401 selected sample treatment (see Subsection 2.3.2). The specific procedures for determining the
402 different validation parameters are summarized in **Table 4S** (see Supplementary Material).

403 *3.3.1. Selectivity*

404 Selectivity was evaluated by comparing the chromatograms and mass spectra of standards in
405 solvents and blanks of honey from the different botanical origins. No matrix interferences were
406 observed at the analytes' retention times (see **Figures 1 and 2S, Supplementary Material**).
407 Moreover, we obtained similar mass spectra for the standards of BPs in solvents and in the
408 matrix extracts (data not shown).

409 *3.3.2. Limits of detection and quantification*

410 The limits of detection (LODs) and quantification (LOQs) are summarized in **Table 1**. They
411 ranged from 0.2 to 1.5 µg/kg and from 0.5 to 4.7 µg/kg, respectively. It should be mentioned
412 that no significant differences in values were observed between honeys of different botanical
413 origins/colours. Those values are below to the SMLs established by legislation (European
414 Commission, 2011, 2018) and are comparable to the best values obtained in previous
415 publications (see Supplementary Material, **Table 1S**). These results demonstrate the excellent
416 sensitivity of the proposed method.

417 *3.3.3. Matrix effect*

418 To ascertain how the matrix influenced the MS signal of the studied compounds, we compared
419 the detector responses (analyte peak area/IS area) of standards in matrix extracts (R_{matrix} ; AF
420 samples) and standards in solvents (R_{solvent}) of the different botanical origins spiked at three
421 different concentrations (low-LOQ (see **Table 1**); medium-50 µg/kg; and high-250 µg/kg). This
422 was calculated as follows: Matrix effect (%) = $[(R_{\text{matrix}}/R_{\text{solvent}}) - 1] \times 100$. Analyte responses at

423 the three levels assayed ranged for most of the BPs between -16% of signal suppression to
424 +18% of signal enhancement (see **Table 5**), except for three of the studied compounds (BPE,
425 BPF and BPS), for which the signal suppression was quite significant in all types of honeys (>
426 30%). These results were confirmed by comparing the slope confidence intervals (SCIs)
427 between standards in solvent and standards in matrix extracts. In all cases, there was an
428 overlapping of SCIs, except for the three indicated BPs (see **Table 1**). Consequently, it can be
429 concluded that the matrix did not significantly affect the BPs signals except for the three
430 previously mentioned compounds.

431 *3.3.4. Linearity/Working range*

432 Standard solvent calibration curves could be used to quantify BPs in all the honeys, except BPE,
433 BPF and BPS that should be quantified with the standard in matrix calibration curves, due to
434 the significant matrix effect observed. However, since the calibration and quantification were
435 done for all the analytes simultaneously, it was necessary to work in the presence of matrix.
436 Calibration curves (n = 6) were constructed by plotting the signal on the y-axis (analyte peak
437 area/IS area) against analyte concentration on the x-axis. Concentration of the analytical curves
438 varied between LOQ and 500 µg/L (LOQ (see **Table 1**), 25, 50, 100, 150, 250, and 500 µg/L),
439 which corresponds to those between LOQ and 250 µg/kg. The graphs obtained in all the
440 calibration curves were straight lines, with the coefficient of the determination values (R^2)
441 higher than 0.99 in all cases (see **Table 1**). Moreover, the deviation of back-calculation
442 concentration from true concentration was lower than 20% (data not shown).

443 *3.3.5. Precision*

444 We conducted concurrent experiments to assess precision, expressed as the relative standard
445 deviation (% RSD). This was achieved through repeated sample analyses using BF samples
446 spiked at three different concentration levels: low-LOQ (see **Table 1**); medium-50 µg/kg; and
447 high-250 µg/kg. These experiments took place either on the same day (repeatability) or over

448 three consecutive days (partial reproducibility). %RSD values were consistently lower than
449 17% in all cases (see Supplementary Material, **Table 5S**).

450 3.3.6. *Trueness*

451 Trueness was evaluated through recovery experiments by comparing the results (analyte peak
452 area/IS area) between BF samples and AF samples, which were obtained from blank samples
453 spiked at three different concentrations (low-LOQ (see **Table 1**); medium-50 µg/kg; and high-
454 250 µg/kg). Mean recoveries for the BPs studied ranged in all cases from 81% to 116%, with
455 %RSD values lower than 17% (see **Table 5**). These recovery values are similar to or even better
456 than those obtained in previous studies (see Supplementary Material, **Table 1S**).

457

458 3.4. Assessment of the applicability of the method

459 The blue applicability grade index (BAGI) was applied in order to evaluate the practicality and
460 applicability of the employed analytical methodology (Manousi, Wojnowski, Płotka-Wasyłka,
461 & Samanidou, 2023). BAGI is a novel and simple to use index that can efficiently assess the
462 applicability of an analytical method. BAGI is complementary to the green assessment tools,
463 and it revolves around the “blue” principles of White Analytical Chemistry, which are mainly
464 related to practical aspects. BAGI considers ten main attributes, such as the type of analysis,
465 the number of analytes that are simultaneously determined, the required instrumentation, or the
466 automation degree, to produce a pictogram and a score that depicts the applicability of an
467 analytical method in terms of practicality. A sequential blue colour scale is used to represent
468 the final score, with colors like dark blue, blue, light blue, and white, which represent high,
469 medium, low, and no compliance with the method's practical criteria, respectively. Moreover,
470 according to BAGI guidelines, it is recommended that the total score to be higher than 60, so
471 that the analytical method can be considered practical (Manousi et al., 2023). Therefore, to

472 calculate the BAGI of the proposed method, its main attributes must be considered. It involved
473 a quantitative, confirmatory, and multi-element analysis of fourteen BPs by UHPLC-MS/MS,
474 with a miniaturized sample preparation (microextraction) allowing for complete analysis of 2-
475 4 samples per hour. In addition, common and commercially available reagents were used. The
476 method involved a minimal sample amount (1.0 g of honey per sample), a preconcentration
477 step, and a semi-automated analysis using an UHPLC autosampler. Taking all these factors into
478 account and the guidelines proposed by Manousi et al. (2023), the method achieved a score of
479 65 (see **Figure 2**), surpassing the 60-point threshold, and demonstrating its applicability.

480

481 3.5. Application of the method

482 The validated method was applied for determining potential BPs residues in 30 honeys from
483 three different botanical origins and colors (see Subsection 2.3.1). Analyses were performed in
484 triplicate and IS was added to all samples at the same concentration (0.1 mg/L). Among the
485 fourteen BPs investigated, residues of nine (BPA, BPAF, BPAP, BPBP, BPFL, BPM, BPP,
486 BPPH, and BPS) were detected in twelve of the samples (see **Figure 3**). It should be specified
487 that in most of the samples the residues of BPs were below the LOQs/LODs, and only BPA
488 was quantified in two of the samples (C9, 12.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$; C11, 12.9 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$), with concentrations
489 lower than the established SML (50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$; European Commission 2018). Analysis of the results
490 indicates that BPS was the most frequently detected BP, found in 40% of the samples (12 out
491 of 30), followed by BPA and BPFL, each detected in 20% of the samples (6 out of 30). With
492 regard to the origin of the samples, it can be concluded that the majority of positive BPs (91%,
493 40 out of 44) were detected in the commercial samples, with residues of BPs found in 56% of
494 positive commercial samples (9 out of 16). In contrast, the number of detected BPs in samples
495 from experimental apiaries was much lower (9%, 4 out of 44 positive BPs), with residues found
496 in only 21% of the analyzed samples (3 out of 14). On the other hand, when considering the

497 material of the honey packaging, residues have been found in both plastic and glass containers
498 without distinction, although it is true that the majority of containers were glass.

499
500 Upon comparing the obtained results with those of previous works (see Supplementary
501 Material, **Table 1S**), it can be deduced that the results regarding the BPS content of commercial
502 honeys are similar to those reported in some studies ($<LOQ-35 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$; Inoue et al., 2003; Khani
503 et al., 2021; Lo Turco et al., 2016), while in other cases the values are much higher ($<LOQ-997$
504 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$; Česen et al., 2016; Meng et al., 2022; Notardonato et al., 2020a,b; Peñalver et al., 2021).
505 It should also be mentioned that in most of the previous studies, only BPA was analyzed or
506 found, consistent with the results in our study. As can be seen, in other studies, the concentration
507 values were higher than the SML in many cases and varied significantly between samples.
508 However, these studies were unable to establish a direct relationship between the BPs content
509 and the botanical origin or the type of packaging, as has happened in our study.

510 Finally, it should be emphasized that in this work, residues of nine different BPs have been
511 determined, which in most cases they were found in concentrations lower than the LOQs,
512 representing the largest number of compounds detected in honey to our knowledge. This
513 underscores the necessity of developing specific and sensitive methodologies for determining
514 these compounds in honey. This statement is supported by the fact that several BPs, especially
515 BPA, have been previously detected in honeys from different countries at variable
516 concentration levels (see Supplementary Material, **Table 1S**).

517

518 **4. Conclusions**

519 A new analytical method, based on solvent microextraction in combination with UHPLC-
520 MS/MS, has been developed and validated for the determination of fourteen BPs in honeys
521 from different botanical origins. The method features an efficient, simple, fast, economical, and

522 environmentally-compatible sample treatment, involving solvent microextraction with acetone
523 and 1-hexanol. With this procedure, not only have excellent recovery percentages been
524 achieved for all the compounds, but the matrix effect has also been minimized for the majority
525 of them (eleven out of fourteen BPs). In this regard, it must be highlighted that to our
526 knowledge, this is the first time that honey from different origins has been taken into account
527 in the development of the sample treatment to determine BPs. In addition, the UHPLC-MS/MS
528 conditions have been specifically developed for this study and cannot be compared with
529 previous works, since it is the first time that such a large number of BPs have been determined
530 simultaneously in honey. The proposed method has been validated, and the results showed that
531 the analytical performance of the method was similar or even better in most cases than previous
532 proposals. The LODs and LOQs obtained were lower than the SMLs established for two of the
533 studied compounds in honey (BPA and BPS), and comparable with the best published values.
534 The proposed method was applied to analyze several commercial and experimental honey
535 samples. Residues of nine BPs were detected in several of the samples at (> LOD), but only
536 BPA was quantified in two of the samples, with a concentration lower than the established
537 SML. Finally, these results justify the hypothesis included in the Introduction concerning the
538 need to develop selective and sensitive methods for determining BPs in honey.

539

540 **Abbreviations**

541 **AF**, samples spiked after sample treatment; **BAGI**, blue applicability grade index; **BF**, samples
542 spiked before sample treatment; **BPA**, bisphenol A; **BPAF**, bisphenol AF; **BPAP**, bisphenol
543 AP; **BPB**, bisphenol B; **BPBP**, bisphenol BP; **BPC**, bisphenol C; **BPE**, bisphenol E, **BPF**,
544 bisphenol F; **BPFL**, bisphenol FL; **BPM**, bisphenol M; **BPP**, bisphenol P; **BPPH**, bisphenol
545 PH; **BPs**, bisphenols; **BPS**, bisphenol S; **BPZ**, bisphenol Z; **DLLME**, dispersive liquid-liquid

546 microextraction; **GC**, gas chromatography; **HPLC**, high performance liquid chromatography;
547 **MRM**, multiple reaction monitoring; **MS/MS**, tandem mass spectrometry; **LOD**, limit of
548 detection; **LOQ**, limit of quantification; *m/z*, mass-to-charge; **RSD**, relative standard deviation;
549 **SE**, solvent extraction; **SML**, specific migration limit; **S/N**, signal-to-noise; **SCI**, slope
550 confidence intervals; **SPE**, solid phase extraction; **UHPLC**, ultra-high-performance liquid
551 chromatography.

552

553 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

554 **Beatriz Martín-Gómez:** Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Writing -
555 original draft, Writing - review & editing.

556 **Silvia Valverde:** Investigation, Methodology, Validation; Visualization, Writing - original
557 draft, Writing - review & editing.

558 **José Bernal:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Validation,
559 Visualization; Writing - original draft; Writing - review & editing.

560 **Ana M. Ares:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project
561 administration, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing - original draft;
562 Writing - review & editing.

563

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571

572 **Conflict of interest statement**

573 The authors of this manuscript declare no conflict of interest.

574

575 **Data availability**

576 The datasets generated during the current study are included in this published article, or they
577 are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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736 **Figure captions**

737 **Figure 1.-** Representative UHPLC-MS/MS chromatograms (MRM mode using the
738 quantification transitions; see **Table 2**) obtained from a blank (analyte free) multifloral honey
739 sample spiked with the selected BPs at 12.5 µg/kg). UHPLC-MS/MS conditions are
740 summarized in Subsection 2.4 and **Table 2**. **BPA**, bisphenol A; **BPAF**, bisphenol AF; **BPAP**,
741 bisphenol AP; **BPB**, bisphenol B; **BPBP**, bisphenol BP; **BPC**, bisphenol C; **BPE**, bisphenol E,
742 **BPF**, bisphenol F; **BPFL**, bisphenol FL; **BPM**, bisphenol M; **BPP**, bisphenol P; **BPPH**,
743 bisphenol PH; **BPS**, bisphenol S; **BPZ**, bisphenol Z; **IS**, BPA-d₁₆ (100 µg/L).

744 **Figure 2.-** BAGI index pictogram of the proposed analytical method.

745 **Figure 3.-** Representative UHPLC-MS/MS chromatograms (MRM mode using the
746 quantification transition; see **Table 2**) obtained from (A) honey sample with endogenous
747 bisphenol A (BPA) content (C9; 12,5 µg/kg), (B) BPA-free multifloral honey sample (E6), (C)
748 BPA-free rosemary honey sample (E3), and (D) BPA-free heather honey sample (E7). UHPLC-
749 MS/MS conditions are summarized in Subsection 2.4 and **Table 2**.

Highlights

- A new method was proposed and validated for determining 14 bisphenols in honeys.
- Sample treatment consists of a solvent extraction with acetone and 1-hexanol.
- Matrix effect was significant ($> 20\%$) for three bisphenols (E, F and S).
- The LOQs were lower than the SMLs established by current legislation.
- Residues of nine bisphenols were detected in some of the analyzed honey samples.

Supplementary Material

**DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF AN ANALYTICAL
METHODOLOGY BASED ON SOLVENT MICROEXTRACTION AND
UHPLC-MS/MS FOR DETERMINING BISPHENOLS IN HONEYS FROM
DIFFERENT BOTANICAL ORIGINS**

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Table 1S.- Published methods for determining bisphenols in honey.

Analytes (SC)	ST (time)	Reagents (g, mL ^{T,O})	ME ^A	Recoveries ^A (%)	LOQs (µg/kg) ^A	VHDO	Residues in samples SC ^{LOD} (µg/kg) ^A	System	Reference
11 (1-7,13,14)	SPE (polymeric) + EV + DER (> 16 h)	133.5 mL (6 mL EA; 3.5 mL ACN; 16.2 MeOH)	NS	20-111	0.1-0.5	No	1,2,7,8,13,14 (<LOQ-302)	GC-MS	(Česen et al., 2016)
6 (1,8)	MISPE (BPA- MIP) + EV (~50 min)	75 mL (5 mL DCM; 9 mL ACN; 0.25 MeOH)	Yes	88-112	2 (LOD)	No	No	HPLC-DAD-MS/MS	(Herrero-Hernández et al., 2009)
2 (1,8)	SPE (polymeric) + EV (~30 min)	25 mL (14 mL MeOH)	No	95-104	NP	No	1 (3-34)	HPLC-FLD	(Inoue et al., 2003)
9 (1)	HLLE-DES- DLLME (~25 min)	6.5 mL (1.5 mL TBAC–DCA–EG DES)	NS	66-103	0.8	No	9-29	GC-MS	(Khani et al., 2021)
26 (1)	SPE (polymeric) + EV (~60 min)	80 mL (13 mL MeOH)	Yes	NP	0.8 (mg/L)	No	No	GC-MS	(Lo Turco et al., 2016)
4 (1,2,8,13)	UA-DLLME (~10 min)	0.5 g, 101.3 mL (1 mL MeOH; 300 µL IOA)	No	87-98	3-20	No	1,28,13 (<LOQ-767)	HPLC-DAD	(Meng et al., 2021)
7 (1)	UVA-DLLME (~50 min)	1 g, ~ 10 mL (75 µL benzene)	Yes	71-76	22	No	20-540	GC-MS/MS	(Notardonato et al., 2020a)
7 (1)	UVA-DLLME (~50 min)	1 g, ~ 10 mL (150 µL toluene)	Yes	70-90	16	No	<LOQ-997	GC-MS/MS	(Notardonato et al., 2020b)
15 (1)	DLLME (~15 min)	~11.6 mL (1.5 mL ACN; 175 CF µL)	Yes	NS	2	No	250-260	GC-MS	(Peñalver et al., 2021)

Table 1S.- Continued.

Analytes (SC)	ST (time)	Reagents (g, mL ^{T,O})	ME ^A	Recoveries ^A	LOQs (µg/kg) ^A	VHDO	Residues in samples SC ^{O,LOD} (µg/kg) ^A	System ^A	Reference
9 (1,8)	RAM (NS)	NS	Yes	96-120	16-22	No	No	HPLC-DAD-MS/MS	(Rodríguez-Gonzalo et al., 2010)
1 (1)	ABS (> 120 min)	> 100 mL	No	78-112	10	Partially	No	HPLC-FLD	(Tian et al., 2018)
4 (1,4,8,13)	SE + SPE (polymeric) + EV (~50 min)	5 g, 50 mL (26 mL ACN)	Yes	NS	NS	No	NS	UHPLC-MS/MS	(Zhou et al., 2019)
14 (1-14)	SE + EV (~15 min)	0.5 g, ~2.5 mL (1.5 mL AC; 35 µL 1HX)	No (1-6,9-12,14) Yes (7,8,13)	81-116	7-14	Yes	<LOQ-13	UHPLC-MS/MS	Present study

^A:data related only to the studied compounds; ^O: organic solvents; ^{O,LOD}: over limit of detection; ^T: total solvents.

1, bisphenol A; **2**, bisphenol AF; **3**, bisphenol AP; **4**, bisphenol B; **5**, bisphenol BP; **6**, bisphenol C; **7**, bisphenol E; **8**, bisphenol F; **9**, bisphenol FL; **10**, bisphenol M; **11**, bisphenol P; **12**, bisphenol PH; **13**, bisphenol S; **14**, bisphenol Z. **ABS**, aqueous biphasic system; **AC**, acetone; **ACN**, acetonitrile; **CF**, chloroform; **CG**, **DAD**, diode array detector; **DCA**, dichloroacetic acid; **DCM**, dichloromethane; **DES**, deep eutectic solvent; **DLLME**, dispersive liquid–liquid microextraction; **EG**, ethylene glycol; **EV**, evaporation; **GC**, gas chromatography; **HLLE**, homogenous liquid–liquid extraction; **HPLC**, high performance liquid chromatography; **1HX**, 1-hexanol; **IOA**, isooctyl alcohol; **LOQ**, limit of quantification; **ME**, matrix effect; **MeOH**, methanol; **MIP**, molecularly imprinted polymer; **MISPE**, molecularly imprinted solid phase extraction; **MS**, mass spectrometry; **MS/MS**, tandem mass spectrometry; **NS**, not specified; **RAM**, restricted access material; **SC**, studied compounds; **SE**, solvent extraction; **SPE**, solid phase extraction; **ST**, sample treatment; **TBAC**, tetrabutyl ammonium chloride; **UA**, ultrasonic assisted; **UHPLC**, ultra-high performance liquid chromatography; **UVA**, ultrasound vortex assisted; **VHDO**, validation for honeys of different origins.

Table 2S- Spiking procedure. Reprinted from Food Chemistry, 408, Adrián Fuente-Ballesteros, Patricia Brugnerotto, Ana C.O. Costa, María J. Nozal, Ana M. Ares, José Bernal, Determination of acaricides in honeys from different botanical origins by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry, 135245, Copyright (2023), with permission from Elsevier.

Description of the spiking procedure

The spiking of the BF samples was done similarly to Jovanov et al. (2014) to assure that the analytes were bound to the honey matrix. Briefly, representative portions of the blank honeys were weighed and transferred to a crystallizer where they were homogeneously spiked with the working standard solutions. The mixtures were then stirred with a glass rod to assist the homogenization and left to equilibrate overnight prior to further analysis. Meanwhile, AF samples were prepared by spiking blank honey samples, which were previously treated with the proposed sample treatment, with working standard solutions that were added to the elution solvent

Table 3S.-Honey samples analyzed in the present study. **BO**, botanical origin; **CIAPA**, Center for Agroenvironmental and Apicultural Investigation; **CO**, country of origin; **CyL**, Castilla y León; **H**, heather; **M**, multifloral; **PV**, País Vasco; **R**, rosemary.

Commercial honeys				Honeys from experimental apiaries			
Sample	Color	CO (BO)	Package	Sample	Color	CO (BO)	Package
C1	white	Finland (M)	Plastic	E1	white	CIAPA (R)	Glass
C2	light amber	Estonia (M)	Paperboard	E2	white	CIAPA (R)	Glass
C3	dark amber	Spain (M)	Glass	E3	white	CIAPA (R)	Glass
C4	light amber	Spain (M)	Glass	E4	light amber	CIAPA (M)	Glass
C5	dark amber	Spain (H)	Glass	E5	light amber	CIAPA (M)	Glass
C6	light amber	Spain (R)	Glass	E6	light amber	CIAPA (M)	Glass
C7	dark amber	Spain (M)	Glass	E7	dark amber	CIAPA (H)	Glass
C8	light amber	Spain (R)	Glass	E8	dark amber	CIAPA (H)	Glass
C9	light amber	Spain (H)	Glass	E9	dark amber	CIAPA (H)	Glass
C10	dark amber	Spain (H)	Glass	E10	dark amber	CyL (M)	Glass
C11	dark amber	Spain (M)	Glass	E11	light amber	CyL (M)	Plastic
C12	dark amber	Spain (M)	Glass	E12	dark amber	CyL (H)	Plastic
C13	light amber	Spain (M)	Glass	E13	White	CyL (R)	Plastic
C14	dark amber	Spain (H)	Glass	E14	White	PV (M)	Glass
C15	light amber	Spain (M)	Paperboard				
C16	light amber	Spain (R)	Glass				

Table 4S.- Procedures employed for determining the validation parameters. Reprinted from Food Chemistry, 408, Adrián Fuente-Ballesteros, Patricia Brugnerotto, Ana C.O. Costa, María J. Nozal, Ana M. Ares, José Bernal, Determination of acaricides in honeys from different botanical origins by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry, 135245, Copyright (2023), with permission from Elsevier.

Validation parameter	Experimental procedure
Selectivity	This was evaluated by comparing the chromatograms and mass spectra of standards in solvents, standard in honey extracts and blank honeys of the three different botanical origins (n = 6).
Limits of detection and quantification	The limits of detection (LODs) and quantification (LOQs) were determined by the injection of several blank sample measurement noise at the elution times for the studied bisphenols and comparing this response (mean values) with the signal (peak heights) of compounds at low concentration levels. The LODs and LOQs were estimated to be three and ten times the S/N ratio, respectively. In addition, it was checked that LOQs met the identification and method performance criteria for recovery (70%-120%) and precision (< 20%).
Matrix effect	To ascertain how the matrix influenced ESI ionization for the bisphenols a comparison was made of the detector responses (analyte peak area/IS area) of standard in solvent and standard in matrix extracts (AF samples) of the different botanical origins spiked at three different concentrations (QC levels). It was calculated as follows: <div style="text-align: center; border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; margin: 10px 0;"> $ME (in\%) = \left(\left(\frac{R_{matrix}}{R_{solvent}} \right) - 1 \right) \times 100$ </div> <p>R_{matrix}: detector response from standard in matrix extract. $R_{solvent}$: detector response from standard in solvent. In addition, the confidence intervals of the slopes in both types of standards were also compared.</p>
Linearity/Working range	Calibration curves (n = 6) were constructed by plotting the signal on the y-axis (analyte peak area/IS area) against the analyte concentration on the x-axis. Linearity was evaluated by visual analysis of the plots, a calculation being made of the determination coefficients (R^2), and by our back calculation of the concentrations of the individual calibration standards.

Table 4S.- Continued.

Validation parameter	Experimental procedure
Precision	Precision, which was expressed as relative standard deviation (% RSD), experiments were performed concurrently by repeated sample analysis using BF samples, either on the same day (repeatability), or over three consecutive days (partial reproducibility).
Trueness	It was evaluated by means of recovery experiments (as a measure of trueness), by comparing the results (analyte peak area/IS area) obtained from blank honey samples spiked at three different concentrations (low, medium and high QC levels), either prior to (BF samples) or following (AF samples) sample treatment.

Table 5S.- Summary of precision studies (minimum and maximum %RSD values) for the determination of bisphenols in spiked blank honey samples.

	Spiking level	Multifloral		Rosemary		Heather	
		Min	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max
Repeatability	Low	3	13	4	16	6	14
	Medium	5	15	5	14	2	16
	High	2	14	3	15	4	15
Partial reproducibility	Low	4	14	3	15	5	15
	Medium	6	16	4	15	3	16
	High	3	12	2	14	2	15

Low- LOQ (see Table 1); **Medium-** 50 µg/kg; **High-** 250 µg/kg.

Figure 1S.- Chemical structure of bisphenols.

Figure 2S.- Representative UHPLC-MS/MS chromatograms (MRM mode using the quantification transitions for each bisphenol; see **Table 2**) obtained from a blank (analyte free) multifloral honey sample. UHPLC-MS/MS conditions are summarized in Subsection 2.4 and **Table 2**. **1**, bisphenol S; **2**, bisphenol F; **3**, bisphenol E; **4**, bisphenol A; **5**, bisphenol B; **6**, bisphenol C; **7**, bisphenol AP; **8**, bisphenol AF; **9**, bisphenol Z; **10**, bisphenol FL; **11**, bisphenol BP; **12**, bisphenol P; **13**, bisphenol M; **14**, bisphenol PH.

